

THE NON-LINEAR MODEL OF GROUNDWATER LEVEL CHANGE DUE TO THE INCREASE IN EVAPORATION UNDER THE EFFECT OF WIND

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Abstract. In this article, the non-linear model of groundwater level change under the influence of wind strength on evaporation processes, groundwater extraction through wells, and precipitation is investigated. It is proposed to study the presented model by transforming it into a linear form using the quasi-linearization method. In this model, the effect of wind is expressed in terms of how it intensifies evaporation and impacts the groundwater level. The given Neumann boundary condition in the problem allows the observation of the water flow rate at the boundaries of the studied area.

Keywords: filtration, wind strength, evaporation, precipitation, quasi-linearization method, free water loss coefficient, water resources, well discharge.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increase in temperature, changes in precipitation, changes in wind strength and direction, caused by climate change, significantly affect groundwater. Water extraction through wells locally reduces the groundwater level. Considering these factors, long-term monitoring and forecasting of groundwater are of great importance for ensuring the safety of water resources. The mathematical model linearized using the quasi-linearization method allows studying the dynamics of groundwater under the influence of wind and other factors. Below is the non-linear mathematical model for long-term monitoring and forecasting of groundwater, based on the factors mentioned above:

$$\frac{\partial h(x,t)}{\partial t} = \frac{k}{\mu} \frac{\partial^2 h(x,t)^2}{\partial x^2} - Q(x,t) + f(x,t) - \omega(h,W) \quad (1)$$

Initial and boundary conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} h(x,0) &= h_0, \\ \left. \frac{k}{\mu} \frac{\partial h(x,t)^2}{\partial x} \right|_{x=0} &= -\xi(h(x,t)^2 - h(x,0)^2), \\ \left. \frac{k}{\mu} \frac{\partial h(x,t)^2}{\partial x} \right|_{x=L} &= \xi(h(x,t)^2 - h(x,0)^2). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

here, $h(x,t)$ represents the groundwater level, k is the filtration coefficient, and $f(x,t)$ is a water source dependent on time and distance (e.g., precipitation), which can be expressed as a sinusoidal function that changes periodically with time [1]: $f(x,t) = f_0 \sin(\frac{2\pi t}{T})$ where f_0 is the maximum precipitation rate and T is the periodicity of precipitation. The function $\omega(h,W)$ is related to wind strength and evaporation and can be expressed as [2]: $\omega(h,W) = \alpha h^2 + \beta Wh$ where α is the general evaporation coefficient related to the square of the water level, β is the coefficient representing the

effect of wind strength on evaporation, and W is the wind strength. μ is the free water loss coefficient, and $Q(x, t)$ is the function representing the effect of water extraction through wells.

2. METODOLOGY

The following methodologies are applied in the research:

Quasi-linearization method: The quasi-linearization method is used to transform the non-linear equation into a linear form [3].

Collection and analysis of data on evaporation, precipitation, and well water extraction volume: Evaporation and precipitation exert external effects on groundwater, while wells extract water from a limited area, reducing the water level locally.

Considering the effect of wind strength and direction: Wind intensifies the evaporation process on the soil surface. Changes in wind strength and direction affect groundwater.

Neumann boundary condition: The Neumann condition is added to control the water flow rate at the boundary points [4].

2.1. Bringing the equation to a dimensionless form and discretization

We bring the given equation to a dimensionless form [4]:

$$h^* = \frac{h}{h_0}, \quad x^* = \frac{x}{L}, \quad y^* = \frac{y}{L}, \quad \tau = \frac{k_0 h_0}{\mu L^2} t, \quad k^* = \frac{k}{k_0}, \quad Q^* = \frac{\mu}{k_0} Q, \quad \omega^* = \frac{\mu}{k_0} \omega, \quad f^* = \frac{\mu}{k_0} f.$$

here, k_0 is the characteristic value of the filtration coefficient, h_0 is the initial groundwater level, and L is the characteristic length of the considered area. Based on the introduced dimensionless quantities, the equation (1) is brought to the following dimensionless form:

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial \tau} = D \frac{\partial^2 h^2}{\partial x^2} - Ah^2 - Bh + f_0 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi\tau}{T_0}\right) - Q_0 \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\gamma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\zeta - \zeta_q)^2}{2\gamma^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

here, $D = \frac{kh_0}{\mu L^2}$, $A = \alpha h_0$, $B = \beta W$.

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{k}{\mu} \frac{\partial h^2}{\partial x} \right|_{x=0} &= -\xi(h_0^2 h^2 - h_0^2), \\ \left. \frac{k}{\mu} \frac{\partial h^2}{\partial x} \right|_{x=1} &= \xi(h_0^2 h^2 - h_0^2). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

We discretize equation (3). The discretized equation, with quasi-linearization, takes the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{h_i^{n+1} - h_i^n}{\Delta \tau} = D \frac{(2\tilde{h}_{i+1} h_i^{n+1} - \tilde{h}_{i+1}^2) - 2(2\tilde{h}_i h_i^{n+1} - \tilde{h}_i^2) + (2\tilde{h}_{i-1} h_i^{n+1} - \tilde{h}_{i-1}^2)}{(\Delta x)^2} - \\ - A(2\tilde{h}_i h_i^{n+1} - \tilde{h}_i^2) - B h_i^{n+1} + f_0 \sin(\omega\tau) - Q_0 \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\gamma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\zeta_i - \zeta_q)^2}{2\gamma^2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

This equation is transformed into a system of three-diagonal equations:

$$a_i h_{i-1}^{n+1} + b_i h_i^{n+1} + c_i h_{i+1}^{n+1} = -d_i \quad (6)$$

here, $a_i = \frac{2D\tilde{h}_{i-1}}{(\Delta x)^2}$, $b_i = \frac{1}{\Delta \tau} + \frac{2D\tilde{h}_i}{(\Delta x)^2} + 2A\tilde{h}_i + B$, $c_i = -\frac{2D\tilde{h}_{i+1}}{(\Delta x)^2}$.

The boundary conditions are discretized as follows:

$$\frac{kh_0^2}{\mu L} \frac{(h_0^{n+1})^2 - 4(h_1^{n+1})^2 + 3(h_2^{n+1})^2}{2\Delta x} = -\xi(h_0^2(h_1^{n+1})^2 - h_0^2),$$

$$\frac{kh_0^2}{\mu L} \frac{-3(h_{I-2}^{n+1})^2 + 4(h_{I-1}^{n+1})^2 - (h_I^{n+1})^2}{2\Delta x} = \xi(h_0^2(h_I^{n+1})^2 - h_0^2). \quad (7)$$

The boundary conditions in (7) are simplified using the quasi-linearization method [4], and based on (6), a system of equations is constructed as follows:

$$\begin{cases} 2\tilde{h}_0 h_0^{n+1} + (2\varphi - 8)\tilde{h}_1 h_1^{n+1} + 6\tilde{h}_2 h_2^{n+1} = \tilde{h}_0^2 + (4 + \varphi)\tilde{h}_1^2 + 3\tilde{h}_2^2 + \varphi, \\ a_i h_{i-1}^{n+1} + b_i h_i^{n+1} + c_i h_{i+1}^{n+1} = -d_i, \\ 2\tilde{h}_{I-2} h_{I-2}^{n+1} + (8 - 2\varphi)\tilde{h}_{I-1} h_{I-1}^{n+1} + 6\tilde{h}_I h_I^{n+1} = \tilde{h}_{I-2}^2 + (4 - \varphi)\tilde{h}_{I-1}^2 + 3\tilde{h}_I^2 - \varphi. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

2.2. Numerical algorithm

The resulting system of equations (7) is solved numerically using the Thomas algorithm [5-8]. The detailed algorithm for numerically solving the problem given below is provided:

Step 1: Define the parameters

Define the physical parameters of the model:

L: Length of the region (meters).

T: Total simulation time (days).

dx: Spatial step size (meters).

dt: Temporal step size (days).

k: Filtration coefficient.

mu: Permeability coefficient of water.

alpha: Evaporation coefficient proportional to wind effect.

beta: Evaporation coefficient relative to wind strength.

W: Wind strength.

f0: Maximum precipitation (dimensionless).

wells: A list of wells with their location and discharge rates.

xi: Boundary condition permeability coefficient.

Step 2: Set up the grid

Create spatial points x from 0 to L with step size dx.

Create time points t from 0 to T with step size dt.

Calculate the number of spatial (N_x) and temporal (N_t) grid points.

Step 3: Check stability criterion

Verify the simulation satisfies the stability condition.

Raise an error if the criterion is violated.

Step 4: Initialize water levels

Set the initial water level at all spatial points to 1 (dimensionless).

Create an empty matrix H to store water levels at all time steps, with the first row initialized to the starting water level.

Step 5: Time iteration

Loop over time steps from $n=1$ to N_t-1 :

Copy the current water level into a new array h_new .

Step 6: Update water levels (Finite difference method)

Loop over spatial points $i=1$ to N_x-2 (excluding boundaries).

Step 7: Add precipitation effect

Compute precipitation at the current time step.

Add the precipitation effect to the water level.

Step 8: Apply well effects

For each well in `wells`:

Find the closest spatial index to the well's location.

Reduce the water level at that index proportional to the well's discharge rate, ensuring the water level does not go negative.

Step 9: Enforce boundary conditions

Update the water levels at the boundaries (0 and L).

Step 10: Update the water level matrix

Copy `h_new` to `h`.

Save the updated water levels in the matrix `H` for the current time step.

Step 11: Plot the Results

Plot the water levels for different time steps.

2.3. Numerical experiments

For numerical experiments, the following calculation parameters are used. The constant parameters in the experiment are [9,10]: the length of the observed area is 1000 meters, the observation time interval is 10 days, the filtration coefficient is 0.01 m/day, the evaporation coefficient under wind influence is 0.01, the evaporation coefficient relative to wind strength is 0.005, the maximum rainfall intensity is 0.01 mm, the free water loss coefficient is 0.3, the spatial step is 10 meters, and the time step is 1 day. The following graphs show the change in water level for different values of wind strength (W):

Figure 1. The numerical solution, at $W = 5$.

Figure 2. The numerical solution, at $W = 10$.

Figure 3. The numerical solution, at $W = 20$.

Figure 4. The numerical solution, at $W = 40$.

The figures depict the change in groundwater level over 3, 6, and 9 days. As shown in the figures, with the increase in wind strength, the water level decreases.

3. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The numerical experiments conducted show that even when the inflow or outflow of water at the boundaries of the observed area follows a nonlinear law, the water level undergoes significant changes under the influence of certain factors. It can be observed that as the discharge rates of the wells increase, the rate of water level decline accelerates.

4. CONCLUSION

Today, forecasting and monitoring water resources is one of the most pressing issues for every country. In this study, a nonlinear model of groundwater levels was developed. An efficient method for solving the model numerically was chosen, and the obtained numerical solutions were analyzed. The analysis reveals that the effect of wind on surface evaporation rates is of significant importance. The increase in evaporation due to wind intensity provides an opportunity to predict the condition of groundwater in a given region. The model described in this article demonstrates, through multiple tests and based on field data, its potential as a tool for addressing practical problems related to groundwater in real-world scenarios.

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